

An Economic Analysis on Marketing of Nutrikraft Poultry Feed in Chandauli District of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:- An economic analysis of the marketing of Nutrikraft poultry feed in Uttar Pradesh's Chandauli District is the focus of the current study. One producer-wholesaler-consumer channel and one producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer channel were discovered to be involved in the marketing of Nutrikraft poultry feed. Channel 2 is the most popular marketing channel among research participants. In channel 1, the overall cost of marketing is Rs 74, the total marketing margin is Rs 270, the channel's marketing effectiveness is 4.12%, and the pricing spread is Rs 194. The pricing spread on channel 2 is Rs. 224, the total marketing cost on channel 2 is Rs. 114, the total marketing margin on channel 2 is Rs. 260, and the marketing efficiency on channel 2 is 3.87%.

Keyword:- Marketing Efficiency, Marketing Margin, Marketing Cost and Price Spread.

I. INTRODUCTION

Food for farm fowl, such as chickens, ducks, geese, and other domestic birds, is known as poultry feed. Prior to the 20th century, chickens were mostly housed on general farms where they foraged for much of their food, eating insects, grain that cows and horses had accidentally spilt, and plants growing nearby. Grain, kitchen trash, calcium supplements like oyster shells, and garden refuse were frequently added to this. Many farms retained flocks that were too big to feed in this way as farming got more specialised, therefore nutritionally complete chicken feed was produced. Grain, protein supplements like soybean oil meal, mineral supplements, and vitamin supplements make up the majority of modern chicken meals. The amount of feed needed and its nutritional needs depend on the weight and age of the chickens, their pace of development, their rate of egg production, the weather (cold or rainy weather promotes higher energy consumption), and the amount of nutrients they forage for. As a result, there are several different feed compositions. Additional variations are introduced when less priced local products are used.

Protein and carbohydrate requirements for healthy chickens must be met, as must the requisite vitamins, dietary minerals, and water. Adding vitamins and minerals to chicken feed through lactose fermentation can help. Calcium is needed by egg-laying chickens in the amount of 4 grammes per day, of which 2 grammes are consumed in each egg. Dietary calcium is frequently obtained from oyster shells. Some diets also call for the inclusion of grit, or small pebbles like bits of granite, in the meal. As food moves through the gizzard, grit grinds it, assisting in digestion. If commercial feed is utilised, grit is not required. As an iodine supplement, calcium iodate is utilised.

Because contaminated feed can infect poultry, feed must always be kept dry and clean. Fungal growth is promoted by damp feed. For instance, mycotoxin poisoning is "one of the most frequent and undoubtedly most under-reported causes of toxicoses in poultry." Maintaining the feed and feeder properly might help prevent diseases. The tool that gives the fowl their food is called a feeder. Feed can be given to chickens that are kept as pets or that are reared privately using jar, trough, or tube feeders. Food obtained via foraging can be used as a supplement to chicken feed. In industrial agriculture, the feeding process is automated with the help of machines, which lowers the cost and expands the size of farming. The biggest expense in commercial chicken raising is the cost of the feed.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Selection of the District:

In the state of Uttar Pradesh, there are 18 divisions and 75 districts. Based on the amount of land that was planted in vegetable, paddy, wheat, and poultry farms, the Uttar Pradesh district of Chandauli was chosen for the current research.

B. Selection of Block:

The district contains 9 blocks. Of them, Chakiya was purposefully chosen for the investigation.

C. Selection of Villages

From the block development office, a comprehensive list of all the villages in the Chakiya block was received. The communities were then ordered in increasing order according to the size of the poultry producing area. In order to conduct the current study, 5% of all communities were randomly chosen.

D. Selection of Respondents:

From the village development office of each chosen village, which provided a list of all the poultry farmers in that village. 10% of the farmers from each village were randomly chosen to be cultivators, and the cultivators were then divided into five groups according to their classification.

Table 1: Selection of Respondents

District	Block	Village Name	Marginal	Small	Semi medium	Medium	Large	Total
Chandauli	Chakiya	Murhhua	4	2	1	3	2	12
		Musahebpur	2	1	1	2	1	7
		Nadawa	3	1	2	1	2	9
		Narharpur	2	1	3	2	1	9
		Pachphriya	3	3	2	1	1	10
		Padari	2	2	1	1	1	7
		Pandi	4	1	2	2	2	11
		Paruhar	2	2	3	2	3	12
		Pipari Khurd	3	3	1	0	1	8
		Pipriya	2	2	0	0	0	4
		Pitpur	1	1	2	0	0	4
		Premapur	1	1	0	0	0	2
		Rampur hamrahi	1	0	0	3	0	4
		Semara	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total			31	20	18	17	14	100

E. Analytical Tools

➤ Mean

$$m = \frac{\text{sum of the terms}}{\text{number of terms}}$$

➤ Marketing Efficiency

$$\frac{(\text{Net price received by producer's} - \text{Consumer price})}{\text{Total marketing cost}}$$

➤ Marketing Cost:

$$\text{Marketing Cost (MC)} = \frac{\Delta TC}{\Delta Q}$$

➤ Marketing Margin

$$\text{Marketing Margin} = \text{Producer price} - \text{Raw material}$$

➤ Price Spread

$$\text{Consumer price} - \text{Net price received by the producer}$$

➤ Market Share:

$$\text{Market Share} = \frac{\text{Company's Revenue (Sales)}}{\text{Entire Market Revenue (Sales)}}$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Reveals the preferred marketing channel by the respondent farmers.

Sr. No.	Channel Type	No of respondent	Percentage
1	Channel - I	15	15.00
2	Channel - II	85	85.00
Total		100	100.00

According to Table 2, there are two marketing channels used in the Chandauli District of Uttar Pradesh to advertise poultry feed. In the study's overall sample of chosen

respondents, Channel II is favoured with a response rate of 85.00 percent, whereas Channel I is preferred with a response rate of 15.00 percent.

Table 3: Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin Marketing Efficiency and Price spread in Channel 1 of marketing of Nutrikraft Poultry feed

Channel -1 (Producer –Wholesaler- Consumer)

S. No	Particulars	Value in Rupees/50kg bag
1.	Producer sale price to wholesaler	1300
2.	Cost incurred by the producer	
i	Packing cost	10.00
ii	Packing material cost	10.00
iii	Transportation cost	12.00
iv	Market cost	10.00
v	Labour cost	07.00
vi	Loading and Unloading cost	05.00
vii	Miscellaneous charges	18.00
viii.	Weighing charges	2.00
	Total cost (i-vii)	74.00
3.	Margin of Producer	150.00

4.	Net price received by producer	1,226
	Margin of Wholesaler	120
5.	Wholesaler sale price to Consumer	1420
•	Total Marketing cost	74
•	Total Marketing Margin	270
•	Marketing Efficiency	4.12%
•	Price Spread	194

Table 3 discloses that the selling price of a 50 kg Nutrikraft poultry feed bag from the producer to the wholesaler is Rs 1300, and the producer's marketing expenses for selling the 50 kg Nutrikraft poultry feed bag to the wholesaler are Rs 74. Nutrikraft chicken feed's producer earned a net price of Rs 1226 for each 50 kilogramme bag. When selling a 50 kilogramme bag of chicken feed, the

producer makes a profit of Rs 150. The cost of a 50 kg Nutrikraft chicken feed bag from the wholesaler to the consumer is Rs 1420; the wholesaler's profit is Rs 120 for each 50 kg bag. In the end, channel 1's total marketing expense was Rs 74, its total marketing profit was Rs 270, its pricing spread was Rs 194, and its marketing effectiveness was 4.12%.

Table 4: Marketing Cost, Marketing Margin Marketing Efficiency and Price spread in Channel 2 of marketing of Nutrikraft Poultry feed

Channel-2: (Producer→Wholesaler→Retailer→Consumer)

Sr.	Particulars	Value in Rs./50kg bag
1a	Producer sale price to Wholesaler	1300
b	Total Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler is	74
c	Margin of the Producer is	150
D	Net price received by producer	1226
2.	Sales price of Wholesaler to Retailer	1400
a.	Cost incurred by the Wholesaler	
I	Loading & Unloading charges	5
Ii	Carriage up to shop	5
Iii	Weighting charges	5
Iv	Town charges	10
V	Transportation	10
Vi	Losses & Miscellaneous charges	5
Total Cost (i-vi)		40.00
Margin of the wholesaler		60.00
3	Margin of Village Merchant/Retailer	50.00
4.	Consumers paid price	1450
•	Total marketing cost	114
•	Total marketing margins	260
•	Marketing Efficiency	3.87%
•	Price Spread	224

Table 4: reveals that the 50 kg Nutrikraft poultry feed bag has a selling price of Rs 1300 from the producer to the wholesaler through channel 2, a marketing cost of Rs 74 for the producer, a profit margin of Rs 150 for the producer over the 50 kg Nutrikraft poultry feed bag, and a net price of Rs 1226 for the producer for marketing the 50 kg Nutrikraft poultry feed bag. The selling price of a 50 kg nutrikraft chicken feed bag from a wholesaler to a retailer is Rs 1400;

the wholesaler's marketing expenses are Rs 40; and the wholesaler's profit margin is Rs 60/bag. Retailer profit per 50 kg of nutrikraft chicken feed is Rs 50; the selling price of the bag from the retailer to the consumer is Rs 1450. In the end, channel 2's entire marketing expenses came to Rs 114, its total marketing profit was Rs 260, its pricing spread was Rs 224, and its marketing effectiveness was 3.87%.

Table 5: Market Share of Nutrikraft Poultry feed in Segment in study area.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Frequency			
		Nutrikraft Poultry Feed	Abis Export Poultry feed	Premium Poultry feed	Eva Poultry feed
1	Nutrient content	10	5	8	7
2	Price	20	13	11	9
3.	Distribution channels	15	13	12	10
4.	Brand Reputation	20	14	11	9
5.	Availability in small packs	40	35	33	25
		95	80	75	60

Table 5 reveals that throughout the research, we discovered a variety of additional chicken feed that the respondents in the study region were using. reveals Nutrikraft's market share in the targeted market sector for chicken feed. The market share of Nutrikraft chicken feed is larger than that of other commonly used poultry feed, as shown in the above table. 95 out of 120 participants in the research region responded to various questions including nutrient content, pricing, distribution channels, brand reputation, and small pack availability. 80 out of 120 respondents in Abis Export poultry feed provided responses, which were divided into several categories. Price13, Brand Reputation14, Distribution Channels13, Nutrient Content5, Price13, and Small Pack 35 are all important factors. In Premium Poultry Feed, a total of 75 out of 120 responses were received in various categories, including Nutrient Content 8, Price 11, Distribution Channels 12, Brand Reputation 11, and Availability in Small Packs 33. In Eva Poultry Feed, a total of 60 responses were received in various categories, including Nutrient Content 7, Price 9, Distribution Channels 10, Brand Reputation 9, and Availability in Small Pack 25. Thus, it can be deduced that Nutrikraft poultry feed has a greater market share in the sector of other poultry feed utilised by respondents in the research region.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, selling chicken feed necessitates a thorough knowledge of the poultry industry and the distinctive dietary requirements of various poultry species. Manufacturers of poultry feed must provide high-quality feed formulas that meet the needs of birds at various phases of growth and health. Building consumer trust and recruiting consumers depend heavily on effective branding and packaging. Poultry feed businesses may set themselves apart from rivals by emphasising the nutritive advantages, quality control procedures, and competitive advantages of their goods.

To effectively reach poultry producers and owners of backyard flocks, marketing strategies should concentrate on targeted advertising through both conventional and digital means. By offering educational tools like seminars, webinars, and instructive materials, a business may become known as an expert in its field and gain the trust of its clients. To effectively reach the target market, it's also important to have strong distribution networks and alliances with feed suppliers, vets, and agricultural retailers.

Poultry feed producers should position themselves as dependable suppliers of high-quality feed by combining product excellence, focused marketing initiatives, and solid customer connections. This will allow them to satisfy the various demands of poultry farmers and contribute to the success of the poultry sector as a whole.

It was established that the marketing of poultry feed involves two channels: channel 1 (producer-wholesaler-consumer) and channel 2 (producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer). Channel 2 is the marketing channel that respondents in the research region most frequently cite as preferable. The pricing spread is Rs. 194 in channel 1, with a total marketing cost of Rs. 74, a total marketing margin of Rs. 270, a marketing efficiency of 4.12%, and a total marketing margin. In channel 2, the overall cost of marketing is Rs. 114, the total marketing margin is Rs. 260, the marketing effectiveness of channel 2 is Rs. 3.87%, and the pricing spread is Rs. 224.

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